

Comparative study on nucleophilic/electrophilic behaviour of divalent organosulfur compounds : A DFT study

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Abstract : Electrophilic/nucleophilic behaviour of twenty-five bivalent organosulfur compounds were studied using global and local DFT based reactivity descriptors at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) and MP2/6-311++G(d,p) levels of theory. Global reactivity descriptors are used to observe overall stability of the compounds and local parameters are used to quantify reactivity of the sulfur center. Further we have observed the effect of solvents, ethanol and water on the reactivity pattern. Gibb's free energy of solvation is used to measure stability of the compounds in solvent phases.

Keywords : DFT, *o*-mercapto azo compounds, sulfenyl halide, HOMO, LUMO, dual descriptor.

Introduction

Sulfur based reagents are profoundly engaged in recreation of new synthetic methodology of organic chemistry¹. Lower ionization energy and greater polarizability of valence shell electrons of the sulfur atom in bivalent organosulfur compounds make most of these compounds nucleophilic in nature². For example, characteristic property of a thiol (RSH) is defined as the ease with which they promote nucleophilic substitution reaction at carbon centers of organic substrates. Thiolate anions (RS⁻) are good soft nucleophiles as compared to thiols³. Sulfides (RSR) also act as moderately reactive nucleophiles. Due to dichotomous polar nature of sulfur atom, both nucleophilic as well as electrophilic attacks are possible at sulfur atom in divalent organosulfur compounds. Attachment of a strong electron withdrawing atom or group to the sulfur atom lowers LUMO energy causing these compounds to act as electrophiles⁴; only S-O, S-N and S-X (where, X are halogens) bonds provide electrophilic sulfur atom in compounds like sulfenic acids, sulfenamides and sulfenyl halides. Sulfenic acids are inherently unstable and sulfenamides are difficult to be synthesized; so sulfenyl halides are mostly used for their synthesis^{5,6}. Only practical sources of electrophilic divalent sulfur compounds are sulfenyl halides. A number of aliphatic and

arene sulfenyl halides are known and their reactions have been extensively studied⁷⁻¹⁶. Sulfenyl fluorides (R-SF) and iodides (R-SI) are too unstable to be synthesized¹⁷⁻²⁰. Consequently, sulfenyl chlorides (R-SCl) and sulfenyl bromides (R-SBr) bear importance in synthetic applications. However, aliphatic sulfenyl halides (R-SX, X = Cl, Br) having α -H atom are prone to Pummerer type rearrangement and hence are unstable. Aromatic sulfenyl halides (X = Cl, Br) are relatively more stable compared to aliphatic one due to absence of α -H atom and d-resonance of sulfur atom with the aromatic system²¹. On the other hand benzenesulfenyl halides (X = Cl, Br) are thermolabile because of dehalogenative dimerization^{22,23}. However, introduction of an *ortho*-aryldio group in benzenesulfenyl halides dramatically change their physical and chemical properties due to existence in benzothiadiazolium salt (BTD-form) structure²⁴. The resulting *ortho*-mercapto azo compounds having soft electrophilic sulfur atom are thermally stable, insensitive to nucleophilic solvent and soluble in warm water.

Density functional theory (DFT) provides a powerful theoretical framework for studying reactivity of molecular systems in terms of global and local reactivity descriptors. These descriptors have been studied widely to examine chemical reactivity and site selectivity of a

molecular system²⁵⁻³². In general, DFT reactivity descriptors are classified as global (GRD) and local reactivity descriptors (LRD)³³. Chemical potential (μ), global hardness (η), global softness (S), global electrophilicity (ω) etc. are global reactivity descriptors and are highly successful in predicting global chemical reactivity trends³⁴⁻³⁶. On the other hand Fukui functions (FF), local softness (s), local electrophilicity (ω), relative nucleophilicity/electrophilicity indices (f^+/f^-), (s^+/s^-), (ω^+/ω^-) and reactivity-selectivity descriptor or dual local Fukui function (Δf), dual local softness (Δs), dual local electrophilicity ($\Delta\omega$) are extensively applied to probe local reactivity. The frontier highest unoccupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest occupied molecular orbital (LUMO) are also used to describe spatial variation of molecular reactivity to electrophilic and nucleophilic attacks³⁷. Understanding of the global, local reactivity descriptors and HOMO-LUMO energies are important to explain their nucleophilic/electrophilic behaviour.

In this article we consider ϵ_{HOMO} , ϵ_{LUMO} , μ , η , ω and $f^\pm$, $\omega^\pm$, $s^\pm$, Δf , $\Delta\omega$, Δs , f^+/f^- , ω^+/ω^- , s^+/s^- to observe the reactivity/stability of randomly selected compounds possessing divalent S-center. Out of these, fifteen compounds including aliphatic (compounds **1-6**), arene (compounds **7-10**) sulfenyl halides, *o*-mercapto azo compounds (**11-15**) possess electrophilic S-center and ten sodium thiolates, possess nucleophilic S-center shown in Scheme A.

Theoretical details of reactivity descriptors :

Conceptual density functional theory defines the chemical potential μ as the first derivative of energy with respect to the number of electrons³⁸.

$$\mu = \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} \quad (1)$$

and global hardness (η)^{39,40}

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial N^2} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} \quad (2)$$

where, E is the energy and N is the number of electrons of an electronic system at constant external potential, $v(\vec{r})$.

In most numerical applications, chemical potential (μ) and chemical hardness (η) are calculated using finite difference approximation in terms of IP and EA and there-

fore, μ and η , given below, can be used as working formulae

$$\mu = \frac{-(\text{IP} + \text{EA})}{2} \quad (3)$$

$$\eta = \frac{(\text{IP} - \text{EA})}{2} \quad (4)$$

The ΔSCF method defines the above quantities in terms of ionization potential (IP) and electron affinity (EA) of the system⁴¹

$$\text{IP} = E_{N-1} - E_N \quad (5)$$

$$\text{EA} = E_N - E_{N+1} \quad (6)$$

where E_{N-1} , E_N and E_{N+1} are energies of N-1, N and N+1 systems respectively.

Thus, once the energies of the neutral (N), cationic (N^+), and anionic (N^-) systems are known, chemical potential and hardness (or softness) values can easily be estimated from the following formulae :

$$\mu = \frac{(E_{N+1} - E_{N-1})}{2} \quad (7)$$

$$\eta = \frac{(E_{N-1} + E_{N+1} - 2E_N)}{2} \quad (8)$$

Global softness (S) is defined as

$$S = \frac{1}{2\eta} \quad (9)$$

Approximations, involving the use of Koopmans' theorem⁴² defines the IP and EA in terms of the energies of highest occupied molecular orbital (ϵ_{HOMO}) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (ϵ_{LUMO}) as

$$\text{IP} = -\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{EA} = -\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} \quad (11)$$

and therefore, μ and η can be expressed as

$$\eta = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} - \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}}{2} \quad (12)$$

and

$$\mu = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} + \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}}{2} \quad (13)$$

Parr and coworkers proposed global electrophilicity (ω)

Electrophilic sulfenyl halides

Nucleophilic sodium thiolates

Scheme A. Structures of bivalent organosulfur compounds having electrophilic and nucleophilic sulfur center.

as a measure of electrophilicity of a ligand as⁴³

$$\omega = \frac{\mu^2}{2\eta} \quad (14)$$

It is the measure of capacity of a species to accept an arbitrary number of electrons. Recently Chattaraj *et al.* proposed a more broad and very general local reactivity descriptor, called philicity, which encompass electrophilic,

nucleophilic and radical reactions⁴⁴. Later Roy *et al.* discussed the limitations of applicability of this index^{45,46}. Local electrophilicity index is defined as⁴⁷

$$\omega_k^\pm = \omega f_k^\pm \quad (15)$$

where, f_k^+ is the electrophilic Fukui function. Later on Chattaraj *et al.*⁴⁴ proposed a generalized concept of philicity containing electrophilic, nucleophilic and radical reactions. The condensed-to-atom variants for the

atomic site k have been written as :

$$\omega_k^\alpha = f_k^\alpha \omega; \alpha = +, -, 0$$

where, $\alpha = +, -$ and 0 refer to nucleophilic, electrophilic and radical attacks respectively.

However, condensed Fukui function (CFF)⁴⁸ is of more significance. For an atom 'x' in a molecule with N electrons in a constant external potential, $v(\vec{r})$ the CFF can be obtained from finite different approximation as,

$$f_x^+ = [\rho_x(N_0 + 1) - \rho_x(N_0)] \quad \text{for nucleophilic attack} \quad (16)$$

$$f_x^- = [\rho_x(N_0) - \rho_x(N_0 - 1)] \quad \text{for electrophilic attack} \quad (17)$$

where, $\rho_x(N_0)$, $\rho_x(N_0 - 1)$ and $\rho_x(N_0 + 1)$ are electronic population on atom x of the molecule with N_0 , $N_0 - 1$ and $N_0 + 1$ electron systems, respectively.

Another important local descriptor is the local softness (s), defined as

$$s^+ = S f_k^\pm \quad (18)$$

Toro-Labbé *et al.*^{25,49} have recently proposed a dual descriptor (Δf), which is defined as the difference between the nucleophilic and electrophilic Fukui functions and is given by,

$$\Delta f = [f^+ - f^-] \quad (19)$$

If $\Delta f > 0$, then the site is favoured for a nucleophilic attack, whereas if $\Delta f < 0$, then the site could hardly be susceptible to undertake a nucleophilic attack but may be favoured for an electrophilic attack. The associated dual local softness has also been defined as³⁴

$$\Delta s = [s^+ - s^-] \quad (20)$$

where, $s^+ = S f_k^+$ and $s^- = S f_k^-$

It is defined as the condensed version of Δf multiplied by the molecular softness S .

Computational details :

Geometrical minima of the sulfenyl halides and sodium thiolates were optimized with 6-311++G(d,p) basis set using Becke three parameter exchange and Lee, Yang and Parr correlation functional, B3LYP^{50,51} and was confirmed by frequency calculations. Thereafter, single point energy calculations were performed on the optimized geometry at the same level of theory in water and ethanol phases using polarizable continuum model⁵²⁻⁵⁴. Global and local reactivity descriptors were calculated

using eqs. (1-14). Free energy of solvation (ΔG_{sol}) in solvent phases was computed using the SMD model proposed by Truhlar and coworkers⁵⁵. Hirshfeld population⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸ analysis were performed to obtain charges at different sites. To observe consistency in results we have repeated our calculations at MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory. All calculations were performed in Gaussian09⁵⁹.

Results and discussion

ϵ_{HOMO} and ϵ_{LUMO} :

Energy of the FMOs (HOMO and LUMO) of a chemical species plays a key role in determining its nucleophilic/electrophilic behaviour. It was earlier demonstrated that polarity of a solvent effects the energy of the FMOs⁶⁰. Higher ϵ_{HOMO} corresponds to more reactive nucleophile while lower ϵ_{LUMO} energy corresponds to more reactive electrophile. Due to dichotomous polar nature of S-center, both nucleophilic and electrophilic attacks are possible at sulfur center of the organosulfur compounds. It is expected that replacement of H-atom of thiol group (-SH) by electron donating group would enhance the nucleophilic nature while replacement by electron withdrawing group would enhance electrophilic nature on S-center.

The ϵ_{HOMO} and ϵ_{LUMO} of 25 bivalent organosulfur compounds, calculated in gas as well as in ethanol and aqueous phases at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory are presented in Fig. 1. It is observed that in gas phase, ϵ_{HOMO} of sodium thiolates (compounds **16-25**) are comparatively higher than that of sulfenyl halides (compounds **1-15**), Fig. 1(a). This facilitates sodium thiolates to act as electron donors. Similar trends were found in ethanol and aqueous phases. However, in polar solvent, ϵ_{HOMO} of sodium thiolates show lower values, Fig. 1(b). Thus, sodium thiolates are stabilized by solvent polarity which in turn reduces nucleophilic nature. Consistent result is observed at MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory Fig. S1(a).

In gas phase, ϵ_{LUMO} of sulfenyl halides exhibit lower value than that of sodium thiolates, with exceptionally lower values shown by 2,4-dinitrophenyl chloride and *p*-nitroazobenzene-2-sulfenyl bromide (compounds **10**, **12**), because of electron withdrawing nature of -NO₂ group, Fig. 1(a). Similar trend is also found in solvent phases, Fig. 1(c). So, compounds **10** and **12** are expected to act as better electrophiles compared to other members. In polar solvent, ϵ_{LUMO} of sodium thiolates show higher

Fig. 1(a-c). HOMO and LUMO energies at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory in gas, ethanol and water phases.

values compared to gas phase, Fig. 1(c). Thus, solvent polarity reduces nucleophilic nature by increasing ϵ_{LUMO} energy. Almost, similar variations of ϵ_{LUMO} of sodium thiolates are observed at MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory.

Global hardness (η) and global electrophilicity (ω) :

Global hardness and electrophilicity quantify susceptibility of a species to donate/accept electron density. Calculated global hardness and global electrophilicity at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory in gas and solvent phases are shown in Fig. 2. It is important to note that sulfenyl halides are harder than sodium thiolates, Fig. 2(a). Hence, sulfenyl halides are expected to behave as better electrophiles as compared to sodium thiolates. However, in solvent phases, hardness of sodium thiolates increases resulting in a decrease in nucleophilicity.

On the other hand, aromatic sulfenyl halides (compounds 7-15) are found to be softer in solvent phases, (shown in box), Figs. 2(b-c) and this effect is expected to be caused by d-resonance.

In general, a nucleophile is characterized by lower value of global electrophilicity (ω) and reverse is true for an electrophile. Gas phase global electrophilicity of the compounds at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory are presented in Fig. 2(d). Except sulfenyl halides (compounds 1, 3 and 4), ω values of all the sulfenyl halides (compounds 2, 5-15) are higher than that of sodium thiolates. However, in solvent phases, ω values of all sulfenyl halides are observed to be higher than that of sodium thiolates, Figs. 2(e-f). Sodium thiolates exhibit lower ω values compared to the sulfenyl halides and we can predict better susceptibility of these compounds to be involved in reactions with electrophiles while sulfenyl compounds could anticipate better susceptibility to be involved in a reaction with nucleophiles.

CFF, local softness, local philicity, relative nucleophilicity and dual descriptors :

Electrophilic/nucleophilic Fukui functions (FFs) have been used as precursor of reactivity to nucleophile/electrophile. Roy *et al.* proposed relative electrophilicity/nucleophilicity based on the ratio of electrophilic/nucleophilic FFs and local softness⁶¹. Toro-Labbé *et al.* proposed dual descriptors Δf and Δs ^{25,49}. Gas phase values of local reactivity descriptors at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory are presented in Table 1. Descriptors f^-/f^+ , ω^-/ω^+ , s^-/s^+ , s^- , Δs provided a better estimation of electrophilic/nucleophilic behavior of the sulfur center.

Fig. S1. HOMO and LUMO energies at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory in gas, ethanol and water phases.

Fig. 2(a-f). Hardness and electrophilicity at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory in gas, ethanol and water phases.

Table 1. Fukui function, local softness, local philicity, relative nucleophilicity, and dual descriptors at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory in gas phase

Sl. no.	f^+	f^-	Δf	f^-/f^+	ω^+	ω^-	$\Delta\omega$	ω^-/ω^+	s^+	s^-	Δs	s^-/s^+
1.	0.256	0.465	-0.208	1.813	0.034	0.062	-0.028	1.813	1.457	2.643	-1.185	1.813
2.	0.364	0.445	-0.081	1.222	0.089	0.109	-0.020	1.222	2.133	2.606	-0.473	1.222
3.	0.265	0.444	-0.179	1.676	0.044	0.074	-0.030	1.676	1.670	2.800	-1.130	1.676
4.	0.246	0.400	-0.154	1.628	0.040	0.065	-0.025	1.628	1.557	2.535	-0.978	1.628
5.	0.299	0.361	-0.062	1.209	0.072	0.087	-0.015	1.209	1.656	2.002	-0.346	1.209
6.	0.306	0.403	-0.097	1.318	0.059	0.078	-0.019	1.318	1.743	2.298	-0.555	1.318
7.	0.262	0.366	-0.105	1.399	0.055	0.077	-0.022	1.399	1.789	2.503	-0.714	1.399
8.	0.082	0.266	-0.184	3.259	0.023	0.074	-0.051	3.259	0.615	2.005	-1.390	3.259
9.	0.190	0.288	-0.098	1.517	0.048	0.073	-0.025	1.517	1.329	2.016	-0.687	1.517
10.	0.080	0.265	-0.185	3.311	0.026	0.088	-0.061	3.311	0.587	1.945	-1.357	3.311
11.	0.082	0.124	-0.041	1.503	0.023	0.034	-0.011	1.503	0.698	1.049	-0.351	1.503
12.	0.064	0.142	-0.077	2.202	0.023	0.051	-0.028	2.202	0.589	1.297	-0.708	2.202
13.	0.078	0.117	-0.038	1.489	0.023	0.034	-0.011	1.489	0.670	0.998	-0.328	1.489
14.	0.081	0.111	-0.030	1.376	0.022	0.030	-0.008	1.376	0.685	0.943	-0.258	1.376
15.	0.073	0.128	-0.055	1.755	0.022	0.038	-0.016	1.755	0.625	1.098	-0.472	1.755
16.	0.058	0.540	-0.482	9.243	0.009	0.083	-0.074	9.243	0.603	5.575	-4.972	9.243
17.	0.046	0.517	-0.471	11.341	0.007	0.079	-0.072	11.341	0.469	5.317	-4.848	11.341
18.	0.046	0.515	-0.469	11.207	0.007	0.079	-0.072	11.207	0.472	5.293	-4.821	11.207
19.	0.048	0.505	-0.457	10.612	0.007	0.073	-0.066	10.612	0.465	4.933	-4.468	10.612
20.	0.046	0.512	-0.466	11.168	0.007	0.079	-0.072	11.168	0.472	5.270	-4.798	11.168
21.	0.040	0.490	-0.450	12.265	0.006	0.071	-0.065	12.265	0.392	4.805	-4.413	12.265
22.	0.046	0.512	-0.466	11.174	0.007	0.078	-0.071	11.174	0.471	5.259	-4.789	11.174
23.	0.047	0.493	-0.445	10.398	0.007	0.070	-0.063	10.398	0.464	4.828	-4.364	10.398
24.	0.044	0.522	-0.478	11.844	0.007	0.082	-0.075	11.844	0.443	5.251	-4.808	11.844
25.	0.032	0.397	-0.365	12.229	0.005	0.058	-0.053	12.229	0.295	3.610	-3.315	12.229

It has been observed that local quantities (f^- and s^-) exhibit expected higher value for S-center in sodium thiolates compared to sulfenyl halide, while BTM form of *o*-mercapto azo compounds (compounds **11-15**) show lower values than aliphatic halides (compounds **1-6**), Table 1, which may be attributed to S-N interaction (weak intramolecular secondary bonding interaction between sulfenyl S-center and N-center of azo moiety) in BTM form. This weak S-N interaction leads to shifting of electron density to the sulfur center from N-center in BTM form leading to reduction of electrophilicity of the sulfur center in aromatic sulfenyl bromide. Because of this interaction, significant increase in S-Br bond distance is observed; S-Br bond in *o*-mercapto azo compounds are in the range 2.44–2.49 Å, compared to a usual S-Br bond (2.18 Å)⁶². Gas phase local softness (s^-) of sodium thiolates are in the range 5.575–3.610 a.u.; comparatively higher than that of

sulfenyl halides (2.800–0.943 a.u.); BTM form of *o*-mercapto azo compounds exhibit lowest values (1.297–0.943 a.u.), Table 1. Thus, it is expected that sodium thiolates act as much better nucleophile while *o*-mercapto azo compounds are better electrophile than aliphatic sulfenyl halides.

Gas phase relative nucleophilicity f^-/f^+ , ω^-/ω^+ and s^-/s^+ values of sodium thiolates are observed to be quite higher compared to sulfenyl halides, Table 1. In ethanol and aqueous phases, these relative nucleophilicity values of sodium thiolates are slightly higher compared to gas phase; representing higher nucleophilicity of the species in respective phases, Tables 2–3.

In gas phase, dual local softness (Δs) value of sodium thiolates are quite high compared to sulfenyl halides, Table 1. Similar trend was observed in case of dual Fukui function (Δf). Chattaraj and coworkers used dual descriptors Δf and Δs to some carbonyl compounds and con-

Table 2. Fukui function, local softness, local philicity, relative nucleophilicity, and dual descriptors at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory in ethanol phase

Sl. no.	f^+	f^-	Δf	f^-/f^+	ω^+	ω^-	$\Delta\omega$	ω^-/ω^+	s^+	s^-	Δs	s^-/s^+
1.	0.378	0.508	-0.130	1.344	0.051	0.068	-0.017	1.344	2.133	2.866	-0.733	1.344
2.	0.399	0.482	-0.083	1.208	0.091	0.110	-0.019	1.208	2.321	2.805	-0.484	1.208
3.	0.374	0.500	-0.126	1.336	0.066	0.088	-0.022	1.336	2.344	3.130	-0.787	1.336
4.	0.340	0.456	-0.116	1.341	0.059	0.079	-0.020	1.341	2.146	2.876	-0.731	1.341
5.	0.334	0.402	-0.068	1.204	0.075	0.091	-0.015	1.204	1.845	2.222	-0.377	1.204
6.	0.375	0.451	-0.075	1.201	0.075	0.090	-0.015	1.201	2.130	2.557	-0.428	1.201
7.	0.319	0.452	-0.132	1.414	0.070	0.099	-0.029	1.414	2.148	3.037	-0.890	1.414
8.	0.087	0.293	-0.206	3.385	0.024	0.080	-0.057	3.385	0.661	2.238	-1.577	3.385
9.	0.127	0.337	-0.210	2.659	0.031	0.084	-0.052	2.659	0.928	2.469	-1.540	2.659
10.	0.086	0.305	-0.219	3.542	0.026	0.091	-0.066	3.542	0.639	2.265	-1.625	3.542
11.	0.104	0.167	-0.063	1.605	0.028	0.045	-0.017	1.605	0.818	1.313	-0.495	1.605
12.	0.079	0.195	-0.116	2.473	0.026	0.065	-0.039	2.473	0.690	1.705	-1.016	2.473
13.	0.100	0.158	-0.058	1.585	0.028	0.044	-0.016	1.585	0.804	1.275	-0.471	1.585
14.	0.103	0.139	-0.037	1.355	0.027	0.037	-0.010	1.355	0.818	1.109	-0.291	1.355
15.	0.093	0.178	-0.085	1.922	0.027	0.052	-0.025	1.922	0.747	1.435	-0.688	1.922
16.	0.041	0.652	-0.611	15.750	0.002	0.039	-0.037	15.750	0.236	3.712	-3.476	15.750
17.	0.034	0.629	-0.595	18.366	0.002	0.037	-0.035	18.366	0.195	3.581	-3.386	18.366
18.	0.034	0.630	-0.596	18.280	0.002	0.037	-0.035	18.280	0.196	3.580	-3.384	18.280
19.	0.030	0.619	-0.588	20.380	0.002	0.037	-0.035	20.380	0.173	3.519	-3.346	20.380
20.	0.034	0.630	-0.596	18.279	0.002	0.037	-0.035	18.279	0.196	3.584	-3.388	18.279
21.	0.027	0.602	-0.575	22.580	0.002	0.037	-0.035	22.580	0.154	3.467	-3.314	22.580
22.	0.035	0.630	-0.596	18.261	0.002	0.037	-0.035	18.261	0.196	3.582	-3.386	18.261
23.	0.029	0.615	-0.586	21.393	0.002	0.036	-0.035	21.393	0.164	3.509	-3.345	21.393
24.	0.035	0.634	-0.599	17.983	0.002	0.038	-0.036	17.983	0.197	3.540	-3.343	17.983
25.	0.032	0.474	-0.442	14.929	0.002	0.031	-0.029	14.929	0.179	2.668	-2.489	14.929

Table 3. Fukui function, local softness, local philicity, relative nucleophilicity, and dual descriptors at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory in aqueous phase

Sl. no.	f^+	f^-	Δf	f^-/f^+	ω^+	ω^-	$\Delta\omega$	ω^-/ω^+	s^+	s^-	Δs	s^-/s^+
1.	0.380	0.510	-0.131	1.344	0.051	0.069	-0.018	1.344	2.141	2.877	-0.736	1.344
2.	0.400	0.484	-0.084	1.209	0.091	0.110	-0.019	1.209	2.329	2.816	-0.487	1.209
3.	0.376	0.503	-0.126	1.335	0.066	0.089	-0.022	1.335	2.357	3.147	-0.790	1.335
4.	0.343	0.459	-0.116	1.340	0.059	0.080	-0.020	1.340	2.160	2.894	-0.734	1.340
5.	0.335	0.404	-0.069	1.205	0.075	0.091	-0.015	1.205	1.854	2.233	-0.379	1.205
6.	0.377	0.453	-0.076	1.201	0.076	0.091	-0.015	1.201	2.140	2.570	-0.430	1.201
7.	0.322	0.456	-0.134	1.415	0.071	0.100	-0.029	1.415	2.165	3.062	-0.898	1.415
8.	0.087	0.294	-0.207	3.387	0.024	0.081	-0.057	3.387	0.664	2.249	-1.585	3.387
9.	0.118	0.339	-0.221	2.871	0.029	0.084	-0.055	2.871	0.869	2.494	-1.626	2.871
10.	0.085	0.307	-0.222	3.605	0.025	0.092	-0.066	3.605	0.633	2.281	-1.649	3.605
11.	0.105	0.169	-0.064	1.608	0.028	0.046	-0.017	1.608	0.826	1.329	-0.502	1.608
12.	0.080	0.198	-0.118	2.484	0.027	0.066	-0.039	2.484	0.696	1.729	-1.033	2.484
13.	0.101	0.161	-0.060	1.589	0.028	0.044	-0.016	1.589	0.813	1.292	-0.479	1.589
14.	0.104	0.140	-0.036	1.347	0.028	0.038	-0.010	1.347	0.899	1.211	-0.312	1.347
15.	0.094	0.181	-0.087	1.929	0.027	0.053	-0.026	1.929	0.755	1.456	-0.702	1.929

Table-3 (contd.)

16.	0.043	0.656	-0.612	15.104	0.003	0.039	-0.036	15.104	0.244	3.687	-3.443	15.104
17.	0.036	0.633	-0.597	17.556	0.002	0.037	-0.035	17.556	0.203	3.559	-3.356	17.556
18.	0.036	0.634	-0.598	17.497	0.002	0.037	-0.035	17.497	0.203	3.558	-3.355	17.497
19.	0.031	0.623	-0.592	20.011	0.002	0.037	-0.035	20.011	0.175	3.503	-3.328	20.011
20.	0.036	0.634	-0.598	17.497	0.002	0.037	-0.035	17.497	0.204	3.561	-3.358	17.497
21.	0.028	0.606	-0.578	21.858	0.002	0.037	-0.035	21.858	0.158	3.454	-3.296	21.858
22.	0.036	0.634	-0.598	17.499	0.002	0.037	-0.035	17.499	0.203	3.559	-3.356	17.499
23.	0.029	0.620	-0.590	21.218	0.002	0.037	-0.035	21.218	0.165	3.494	-3.329	21.218
24.	0.037	0.638	-0.601	17.215	0.002	0.038	-0.036	17.215	0.204	3.520	-3.316	17.215
25.	0.033	0.477	-0.445	14.669	0.002	0.031	-0.029	14.669	0.184	2.703	-2.519	14.669

cluded that, sites with $\Delta s > 0$ act as electrophiles whereas sites with $\Delta s < 0$ act as a nucleophiles^{25,34}. All organosulfur compounds studied here possess $\Delta s < 0$. Δs value of sodium thiolates are quite high and is found to be in the range -3.315 to -4.972 followed by sulfenyl halides with Δs ranging from -0.258 to -1.390. Similar trends were found in ethanol and aqueous phases (Tables 2 and 3). MP2/6-311++G (d,p) level of theory showed consistent result at of B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p) level of theory in all phases. [Tables S1-S3]. Thus, S-center of sodium thiolates are expected to be a better nucleophiles whereas S-center of sulfenyl halides are expected to be electrophiles.

Free energy of solvation (ΔG_{sol}) :

Free energy of solvation (ΔG_{sol}) provides valuable information regarding the stability of molecular systems in a particular solvent. Calculated ΔG_{sol} of the investigated compounds in two solvents, ethanol ($\Delta G_{sol,et}$) and water ($\Delta G_{sol,wa}$) at B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p) and MP2/6-311++G (d,p) levels of theory are represented in Table 4. In both phases, it was significantly found that ΔG_{sol} values of sodium thiolates are quite higher than sulfenyl halides. In case of sulfenyl halides, ΔG_{sol} is in the order, *o*-mercapto azo compounds > arene sulfenyl halides > aliphatic sulfenyl halides. Importantly, in case of sulfenyl halides, $\Delta G_{sol,et}$ is considerably higher than $\Delta G_{sol,wa}$.

Table S1. Fukui function, local softness, local philicity, relative nucleophilicity, and dual descriptors at MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory in gas phase

Sl. no.	f^+	f^-	Δf	f^-/f^+	ω^+	ω^-	$\Delta\omega$	ω^-/ω^+	s^+	s^-	Δs	s^-/s^+
1.	0.352	0.538	-0.185	1.527	0.023	0.035	-0.012	1.527	0.890	1.358	-0.469	1.527
2.	0.389	0.537	-0.148	1.379	0.033	0.046	-0.013	1.379	0.877	1.209	-0.332	1.379
3.	0.353	0.523	-0.170	1.482	0.023	0.034	-0.011	1.482	0.882	1.308	-0.425	1.482
4.	0.326	0.496	-0.170	1.523	0.021	0.032	-0.011	1.523	0.826	1.259	-0.432	1.523
5.	0.336	0.483	-0.147	1.436	0.028	0.041	-0.012	1.436	0.750	1.078	-0.328	1.436
6.	0.368	0.514	-0.147	1.400	0.027	0.038	-0.011	1.400	0.856	1.198	-0.342	1.400
7.	0.325	0.504	-0.179	1.551	0.022	0.034	-0.012	1.551	0.828	1.285	-0.457	1.551
8.	0.041	0.385	-0.344	9.393	0.003	0.031	-0.028	9.393	0.114	1.075	-0.960	9.393
9.	0.055	0.381	-0.326	6.924	0.004	0.029	-0.025	6.924	0.147	1.021	-0.874	6.924
10.	0.043	0.392	-0.349	9.101	0.004	0.040	-0.036	9.101	0.118	1.070	-0.952	9.101
11.	0.068	0.274	-0.206	4.039	0.005	0.022	-0.016	4.039	0.207	0.838	-0.630	4.039
12.	0.060	0.283	-0.223	4.740	0.006	0.029	-0.023	4.740	0.187	0.887	-0.700	4.740
13.	0.065	0.282	-0.217	4.334	0.005	0.024	-0.018	4.334	0.201	0.871	-0.670	4.334
14.	0.075	0.277	-0.202	3.703	0.006	0.021	-0.015	3.703	0.231	0.856	-0.625	3.703
15.	0.071	0.216	-0.145	3.059	0.006	0.019	-0.012	3.059	0.214	0.655	-0.441	3.059
16.	0.029	0.602	-0.573	20.694	0.002	0.049	-0.046	20.694	0.117	2.429	-2.311	20.694
17.	0.022	0.581	-0.559	26.989	0.002	0.047	-0.045	26.989	0.087	2.343	-2.256	26.989
18.	0.021	0.579	-0.558	27.506	0.002	0.047	-0.045	27.506	0.085	2.335	-2.250	27.506

Table-S1 (contd.)

19.	0.024	0.569	-0.545	23.996	0.002	0.045	-0.043	23.996	0.094	2.260	-2.166	23.996
20.	0.021	0.577	-0.556	27.766	0.002	0.047	-0.045	27.766	0.084	2.325	-2.242	27.766
21.	0.018	0.553	-0.535	30.843	0.001	0.044	-0.042	30.843	0.071	2.195	-2.124	30.843
22.	0.021	0.576	-0.556	27.866	0.002	0.047	-0.045	27.866	0.083	2.323	-2.239	27.866
23.	0.023	0.564	-0.541	24.131	0.002	0.044	-0.042	24.131	0.093	2.245	-2.152	24.131
24.	0.020	0.587	-0.567	28.771	0.002	0.049	-0.047	28.771	0.081	2.326	-2.245	28.771
25.	0.020	0.537	-0.517	26.267	0.002	0.041	-0.040	26.267	0.083	2.179	-2.096	26.267

Table S2. Fukui function, local softness, local philicity, relative nucleophilicity, and dual descriptors at MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory in ethanol phase

Sl. no.	f^+	f^-	Δf	f^-/f^+	ω^+	ω^-	$\Delta\omega$	ω^-/ω^+	s^+	s^-	Δs	s^-/s^+
1.	0.394	0.586	-0.192	1.487	0.024	0.035	-0.012	1.487	0.967	1.438	-0.471	1.487
2.	0.417	0.581	-0.164	1.394	0.033	0.046	-0.013	1.394	0.937	1.306	-0.369	1.394
3.	0.396	0.575	-0.179	1.453	0.025	0.036	-0.011	1.453	0.957	1.391	-0.434	1.453
4.	0.366	0.545	-0.178	1.486	0.023	0.034	-0.011	1.486	0.900	1.338	-0.437	1.486
5.	0.365	0.528	-0.163	1.448	0.029	0.041	-0.013	1.448	0.815	1.179	-0.365	1.448
6.	0.402	0.562	-0.161	1.400	0.028	0.039	-0.011	1.400	0.906	1.269	-0.363	1.400
7.	0.370	0.559	-0.189	1.510	0.025	0.038	-0.013	1.510	0.961	1.451	-0.490	1.510
8.	0.041	0.385	-0.344	9.393	0.003	0.030	-0.027	9.393	0.115	1.083	-0.968	9.393
9.	0.055	0.381	-0.326	6.924	0.004	0.027	-0.023	6.924	0.150	1.041	-0.891	6.924
10.	0.059	0.444	-0.384	7.465	0.005	0.040	-0.034	7.465	0.163	1.215	-1.052	7.465
11.	0.097	0.140	-0.043	1.443	0.008	0.011	-0.003	1.443	0.295	0.425	-0.131	1.443
12.	0.086	0.144	-0.059	1.683	0.008	0.014	-0.006	1.683	0.267	0.450	-0.183	1.683
13.	0.092	0.141	-0.049	1.535	0.007	0.011	-0.004	1.535	0.281	0.432	-0.151	1.535
14.	0.099	0.141	-0.042	1.418	0.007	0.011	-0.003	1.418	0.307	0.436	-0.129	1.418
15.	0.097	0.140	-0.043	1.443	0.008	0.012	-0.004	1.443	0.292	0.422	-0.130	1.443
16.	0.021	0.682	-0.661	31.776	0.001	0.044	-0.043	31.776	0.070	2.217	-2.147	31.776
17.	0.019	0.664	-0.645	34.882	0.001	0.043	-0.042	34.882	0.062	2.164	-2.102	34.882
18.	0.019	0.664	-0.645	35.021	0.001	0.043	-0.042	35.021	0.062	2.169	-2.108	35.021
19.	0.016	0.657	-0.641	40.888	0.001	0.042	-0.041	40.888	0.052	2.141	-2.089	40.888
20.	0.019	0.664	-0.645	35.043	0.001	0.043	-0.042	35.043	0.062	2.171	-2.109	35.043
21.	0.014	0.640	-0.625	44.531	0.001	0.041	-0.040	44.531	0.047	2.091	-2.044	44.531
22.	0.019	0.665	-0.646	34.979	0.001	0.043	-0.042	34.979	0.062	2.171	-2.109	34.979
23.	0.016	0.658	-0.642	41.679	0.001	0.042	-0.041	41.679	0.052	2.151	-2.099	41.679
24.	0.019	0.668	-0.649	35.330	0.001	0.044	-0.043	35.330	0.061	2.154	-2.093	35.330
25.	0.016	0.646	-0.631	41.453	0.001	0.039	-0.038	41.453	0.054	2.220	-2.166	41.453

Table S3. Fukui function, local softness, local philicity, relative nucleophilicity, and dual descriptors at MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory in aqueous phase

Sl. no.	f^+	f^-	Δf	f^-/f^+	ω^+	ω^-	$\Delta\omega$	ω^-/ω^+	s^+	s^-	Δs	s^-/s^+
1.	0.395	0.588	-0.192	1.487	0.051	0.069	-0.018	1.344	2.141	2.877	-0.736	1.344
2.	0.418	0.583	-0.165	1.395	0.091	0.110	-0.019	1.209	2.329	2.816	-0.487	1.209
3.	0.398	0.578	-0.180	1.453	0.066	0.089	-0.022	1.335	2.357	3.147	-0.790	1.335
4.	0.369	0.547	-0.179	1.485	0.059	0.080	-0.020	1.340	2.160	2.894	-0.734	1.340
5.	0.366	0.530	-0.164	1.448	0.075	0.091	-0.015	1.205	1.854	2.233	-0.379	1.205
6.	0.403	0.565	-0.161	1.401	0.076	0.091	-0.015	1.201	2.140	2.570	-0.430	1.201
7.	0.372	0.562	-0.190	1.509	0.071	0.100	-0.029	1.415	2.165	3.062	-0.898	1.415

Table-S3 (contd.)

8.	0.054	0.436	-0.381	8.013	0.024	0.081	-0.057	3.387	0.664	2.249	-1.585	3.387
9.	0.036	0.466	-0.429	12.787	0.029	0.084	-0.055	2.871	0.869	2.494	-1.626	2.871
10.	0.060	0.446	-0.386	7.388	0.025	0.092	-0.066	3.605	0.633	2.281	-1.649	3.605
11.	0.098	0.138	-0.040	1.407	0.028	0.046	-0.017	1.608	0.826	1.329	-0.502	1.608
12.	0.087	0.143	-0.056	1.643	0.027	0.066	-0.039	2.484	0.696	1.729	-1.033	2.484
13.	0.093	0.139	-0.046	1.497	0.028	0.044	-0.016	1.589	0.813	1.292	-0.479	1.589
14.	0.099	0.141	-0.041	1.417	0.028	0.038	-0.010	1.347	0.899	1.211	-0.312	1.347
15.	0.098	0.138	-0.040	1.408	0.027	0.053	-0.026	1.929	0.755	1.456	-0.702	1.929
16.	0.022	0.685	-0.663	31.181	0.003	0.039	-0.036	15.104	0.244	3.687	-3.443	15.104
17.	0.020	0.667	-0.647	33.861	0.002	0.037	-0.035	17.556	0.203	3.559	-3.356	17.556
18.	0.020	0.668	-0.648	34.041	0.002	0.037	-0.035	17.497	0.203	3.558	-3.355	17.497
19.	0.016	0.661	-0.644	40.439	0.002	0.037	-0.035	20.011	0.175	3.503	-3.328	20.011
20.	0.020	0.668	-0.648	34.057	0.002	0.037	-0.035	17.497	0.204	3.561	-3.358	17.497
21.	0.015	0.643	-0.628	43.183	0.002	0.037	-0.035	21.858	0.158	3.454	-3.296	21.858
22.	0.020	0.668	-0.648	34.057	0.002	0.037	-0.035	17.499	0.203	3.559	-3.356	17.499
23.	0.016	0.661	-0.646	41.492	0.002	0.037	-0.035	21.218	0.165	3.494	-3.329	21.218
24.	0.019	0.671	-0.652	34.431	0.002	0.038	-0.036	17.215	0.204	3.520	-3.316	17.215
25.	0.015	0.650	-0.635	42.341	0.002	0.031	-0.029	14.669	0.184	2.703	-2.519	14.669

Table 4. Solvation energy, ΔG_{sol} (in kcal/mol), at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) and MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory (et = ethanol, wa = water)

Sl. no.	B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)		MP2/6-311++G(d,p)	
	$\Delta G_{\text{sol,et}}$	$\Delta G_{\text{sol,wa}}$	$\Delta G_{\text{sol,et}}$	$\Delta G_{\text{sol,wa}}$
1.	-4.67	-1.57	-4.41	-1.31
2.	-1.86	1.92	-1.84	1.94
3.	-6.87	-1.60	-6.54	-1.26
4.	-7.43	-1.67	-7.08	-1.31
5.	-5.95	-2.28	-5.34	-2.75
6.	-4.93	-2.44	-4.40	-1.81
7.	-7.52	-2.61	-7.07	-2.14
8.	-7.17	-3.07	-5.91	-1.63
9.	-7.91	-3.80	-6.42	-2.09
10.	-7.69	-4.14	-5.09	-1.18
11.	-12.65	-6.79	-12.91	-7.06
12.	-13.37	-8.11	-11.91	-6.43
13.	-13.14	-6.60	-13.03	-6.49
14.	-13.23	-6.72	-13.22	-6.71
15.	-14.77	-8.31	-13.75	-7.12
16.	-18.55	-18.32	-20.27	-20.08
17.	-19.04	-18.01	-20.67	-19.68
18.	-19.55	-17.84	-21.18	-19.51
19.	-18.86	-17.25	-20.35	-18.79
20.	-20.05	-17.64	-21.67	-19.31
21.	-18.81	-16.70	-20.20	-18.13
22.	-20.57	-17.47	-22.19	-19.14
23.	-20.55	-17.51	-21.97	-18.97
24.	-23.95	-23.96	-25.54	-25.57
25.	-19.85	-34.11	-20.75	-35.37

however, in case of sodium thiolates, $\Delta G_{\text{sol,et}} \approx \Delta G_{\text{sol,wa}}$. Influence of solvent polarity on the stability of the compounds is thus observed.

Conclusion

In our present investigation we have observed the reactivity/stability of 25 bivalent organosulfur compounds having different substituent. Our study reveals that -

- (i) HOMO energy of sodium thiolates are comparatively higher than that of sulfenyl halides in all phases. Polar solvents reduce nucleophilicity of sodium-thiolates by lowering ϵ_{HOMO} ; while ϵ_{LUMO} is in reverse manner. Sulfenyl halides (compounds **10**, **12**) with EWG exhibit lower ϵ_{LUMO} value providing a better electrophilic sulfur center. Polar solvents reduce nucleophilicity of sodium thiolates by increasing ϵ_{LUMO} .
- (ii) In gas phase, sulfenyl halides are observed to be harder than sodium thiolates. However, in solvent phases, hardness of sodium thiolates increase whereas hardness of *o*-mercapto azo compounds (compounds **11-15**) decreases.
- (iii) Relative nucleophilicity (f^-/f^+ , ω^-/ω^+ , s^-/s^+) of sulfenyl halides are quite lower than that of sodium thiolates. This suggests that sulfenyl halides will act as electrophiles.

- (iv) All the compounds exhibit negative values for reactivity-selectivity descriptors (Δf , $\Delta\omega$ and Δs) of sulfur center. Local softness values of sulfenyl halides are quite lower than sodium thiolates.
- (v) Higher values of ΔG_{sol} of sodium thiolates are observed compared to sulfenyl halides. This indicates more stability of sodium thiolates. Again, *o*-mercapto azo compounds are more stable than arene and aliphatic sulfenyl halides.

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